

EFFECT OF SHOCK CONTROL BUMPS ON OBLIQUE SHOCK WAVE TURBULENT BOUNDARY LAYER INTERACTIONS

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ABSTRACT

The interaction between a shock wave and a boundary layer is a topic of primary relevance in high-speed aerodynamics, as it may deteriorate the vehicle performance, and can even lead to structural damage. Over the years, many researchers have therefore focused on techniques to mitigate the detrimental effects of such shock wave boundary layer interactions (SWBLI) and a variety of control strategies have been investigated. In this experimental study the effect of shock control bumps (SCBs) on oblique shock wave/boundary layer interactions is investigated, notably the influence of the position where the shock impinges with respect of the bump. The experiments are conducted in the ST-15 wind-tunnel at the Delft University of Technology for fully developed turbulent boundary layer conditions with Re_θ of 21.8×10^3 and Mach number of 2. The effectiveness is assessed by looking at the size of the separated flow region, as well as the downstream boundary layer velocity profile. For this, stereo-PIV is employed as the main diagnostic method to characterise the three-dimensional flow field. In addition to this, high-speed Schlieren measurements are performed to assess the SCB performance, as well as the influence of the shock impingement location on the bump surface, on reducing the separation shock unsteadiness.

1. INTRODUCTION

The occurrence of shock waves is a prominent feature of high speed flight, and the possible interaction between shocks and the boundary layer is relevant for a wide range of aerospace applications such as transonic wings, rocket nozzles, supersonic engine inlets, and high-performance compressor or turbine cascades. The pressure rise im-

posed by the shock wave on the boundary layer can lead to separation which is often unsteady in character. This results in undesirable effects such as large mechanical and thermal loads on the structure due to the unstable dynamics of shock wave boundary layer interactions (SWBLI) [7] [9] or significant decrease in the effective engine inlet area which might even cause an engine unstart [9].

Over the years, much research has been devoted to investigate control methods to suppress the undesired effects of the SWBLI. Most of these methods aim to act on the low momentum region of the boundary layer. Some, such as boundary layer bleed, aim to mitigate the negative effects by removing the low momentum portion of the boundary layer, thus making it fuller in shape, and hence more resistant to separation. However, the loss of mass flow is undesirable since it would need to be compensated by increase of the frontal area of the engine inlet with associated increase in weight and drag [12].

Another approach which has been widely investigated over the years by different research groups is the use of micro vortex generators. Implementing sub-boundary layer level vortex generators rose from the idea of energizing the boundary layer with counter rotating vortices without introducing strong adverse effects on drag. One type of device for SWBLI control that received wide attention is the micro ramp, in view of its structural robustness. Blinde et al. [2], studied micro ramp geometries in an incident shock wave/boundary layer interaction with $M=1.84$ by means of stereo-PIV in planes parallel to the wall and they reported up to 30% reduction in the separated flow at the measurement plane. In [1] Babinsky et al. observed that with the micro ramp control the separated flow region, which was primarily two-dimensional, was broken into three-dimensional separated flow cells.

Giepmans et al. [9] investigated the effect of location and size of the micro-ramps and reported that boundary layer health was improved in the downstream centerline of the micro-ramps with all heights of micro ramps. However, off-centerline measurements indicated an increase in the separated flow region up to 12% for the measurements taken at 50% of the span.

An alternative method to alleviate the unfavourable effects of the shock wave boundary layer interactions is by controlling the shock formation. Due to its geometry, shock control bumps (SCB) are used for reducing the wave drag of especially transonic wings by means of modifying the shock structure. The bump generates quasi-isentropic compression waves upstream of the normal shock wave resulting in a λ -shock configuration. The flow passing through these isentropic compression waves gradually decreases its velocity; thus, the bump partly eliminates the abrupt effects caused by a single, strong normal shock wave.

In [11] Ogawa et al. investigated different three-dimensional bump geometries in a $M=1.3$ flow. They observed the dependence of the shock structure in relation to the impingement location on the bump surface. It was found that when the shock impinges on the upstream part of the bump, re-accelerated flow can create a “supersonic tongue” downstream and thus undesired secondary shock structures and an increase in the wave drag might occur [11]. In contrast, downstream impinging shock can cause a secondary λ -shock structure formation due to the expansion of the flow passing over the crest of the bump. This type of interaction would result in an increase in the total pressure loss [11]. From this, one can conclude that the shock impingement position has a significant importance for mitigating the stagnation pressure losses.

It was also observed that the 3D SCB introduces streamwise vortices in the flow downstream of the bump [10], [11], [13]. For off-design conditions, these vortex pairs will arise from the separated region on the bump surface. Instead, there have been various suggestions by different study groups to explain the mechanism behind the vortices occurring at the design conditions [3], [8], [13]. Colliss et al. [6] related the streamwise vortices to the spanwise pressure gradient on the ramp part of the bump, which was mentioned by Bruce and Colliss as the most convincing evidence [4].

Whereas most studies on the effects of SCB have been for normal shock wave boundary layer interactions, relatively limited research has focused on the flow structures generated by the combination of oblique SWBLIs and shock control bumps. Considering the shape of the SCB, its effect is expected to downsize the separation by “filling” the separation bubble with the bump structure. In addition, the streamwise vortices introduced to the downstream of the interaction by the 3D SCB, would promote a faster recovery of the boundary layer flow. Moreover,

the gradual flow expansion caused by the tail portion of the bump also contributes to a faster flow recovery and providing a fuller velocity profile in respect to the uncontrolled case.

In this work, an experimental study is carried out aiming to improve the understanding of the flow physics associated to the application of 3D SCB in oblique shock wave turbulent boundary layer interactions. More in particular, the effects of SCB and the influence of different relative shock impingement locations, on the unsteady dynamics of the SWBLI are investigated, by means of high speed Schlieren measurements. Quantitative information on the three-dimensional flow field is obtained from stereo-PIV measurements. With this data, a further quantification of the separation behaviour for cases with different impingement location over the bump is carried out through the separation probability concept as introduced by Giepmans et al. in [9].

2. EXPERIMENTAL ARRANGEMENT

2.1 Flow facility and experimental investigation

The experiments were carried out in the ST-15 blow-down supersonic wind-tunnel of the Delft University of Technology. The test section of the tunnel has dimensions of 150mm x 150 mm and has glass windows in the side walls which allow optical access. In the experiments, the tunnel is operated at a Mach number of 2, a total pressure P_0 of 3 bars and a total temperature T_0 of approximately 290 K. In [2] Giepmans et al investigated the effects of location and size of micro-ramp vortex generators in the same facility at similar operating conditions and have also documented undisturbed boundary layer parameters. A summary of the main flow conditions is given in the Table 1.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
M_∞	2.0	δ_i	0.63
U_∞ [m/s]	520	θ_i	0.52
P_0 [N/m ²]	3×10^5	H_i	1.23
T_0 [K]	290	Re	42×10^6
δ_{99} [mm]	5.2	Re_θ	21.8×10^3

Table 1: Experimental conditions and undisturbed boundary layer properties [9]

The bottom wall of the tunnel, where the boundary layer thickness is approximately $\delta_{99}=5.2\text{mm}$ [9], is used to assess the uncontrolled flow field. Afterwards, a shock control bump is installed on this wall by using double sided adhesive tape. For all the cases, the incident shock is generated by installing a 12 degree shock generator.

2.2 Shock control bump specifications

Bruce and Colliss indicated in their review [4] that most of the research on SCB agrees that the optimum performance is achieved when the bump height is of the order of the boundary layer thickness height. While designing the geometry of the bump for the current study this guideline has taken into consideration. The height at the bump crest has been selected as 4.7 mm and the ramp angle is set to 5.7° . The bump has been installed on the wind tunnel lower wall such that the symmetry plane of the bump coincides with that of the test section.

Figure 1: Geometrical parameters of SCB.

The shock impingement location on the bump surface has been introduced as another crucial criteria to determine the efficiency of the bump. Ogawa et al. [11] defined an optimum location for shock impingement as the one that results in the largest λ -shock structure without introducing secondary shocks. When the shock is positioned further upstream of this location it is expected to introduce a secondary shock system as a result of the re-expansion of the flow after the initial shock interaction. On contrary, when the shock impinges downstream of the defined optimum location, the supersonic flow region behind the λ -shock foot accelerates due to the expansion over the bump crest which can lead to secondary shock structures as well as flow separation. In [3] Bruce and Babinsky revealed that 10-15 % difference in the shock position around the crest has significant effects on the flow.

For this investigation, three inviscid impingement locations on the bump were defined (See Fig. 3). A first control impingement location is defined 1.5δ upstream of the first point where the bump has a maximum height. This corresponds to 9.2δ distance from the leading edge of the bump. Additionally, impingement locations 1.5δ downstream and 1δ upstream of this point are investigated. These will be referred to as downstream impingement location and upstream impingement location in the following of the discussion. The incident shock impingement locations were decided regarding the previously mentioned studies which have been conducted on normal shock-boundary layer interactions [3], [5]. In this way, the sensitivity of the shock control bump location for flow control can be investigated.

2.3 Experimental setup

Two main flow diagnostic methods are used in this study, high-speed Schlieren visualization and stereoscopic PIV (sPIV).

High-speed Schlieren is used to resolve the unsteady dynamics of the SWBLI. A LaVision ProHS camera is used with an acquisition frequency of 2800 Hz which is sufficient to resolve the major separation shock unsteadiness.

Figure 2: Setup of sPIV experiments.

To capture the three-dimensional nature of the flow field resulting from the SCB, sPIV measurements were employed. The set-up for the sPIV is shown schematically in Fig. 2, indicating two LaVision sCMOS cameras. On both cameras a 60 mm Nikkor objective was used with $f\#$ set to 8. Due to the configuration of the system, there is an offset angle between the lens plane and the image plane, and a Scheimpflug adapter was added on each lens to impose a collinear condition on the lens and sensor plane. To increase the data acquisition and processing speed cropping applied to the images. This resulted in the Field of View (FOV) of 141.5×41.5 mm and a digital resolution of 19 pixels/mm. For the illumination, a Quantel Evergreen double-pulsed Nd:YAG laser is used, operating at a pulse energy of 200 mJ/pulse with a repetition rate of 15 Hz. For all the measurements the pulse separation is set to $1 \mu s$. Measurements were carried out in the symmetry plane of the bump, as well as in a plane at a distance of 5.8δ from the symmetry plane.

Data acquisition and processing is done in DaVis 8.4.0. As the first step a Butterworth high pass filter is applied to filter the reflections. Additionally, for the pre-processing the particle intensity was normalized using min/max filtering. Next, a multi pass cross-correlation with 48×48 pixels and 24×24 pixels respectively, with 75% overlap were applied. This resulted in a vector pitch of 0.3 mm. As final step, the universal outlier detection approach was applied, as implemented in DaVis. Average velocity field and standard deviation of the vector field are also obtained through DaVis. To do so, a requirement of having at least 50 source vectors at each position to compute results is implemented.

Figure 3: Measurement planes and shock impingement locations on the bump.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Effects of the shock control bump on the flow organization

(a) Uncontrolled case.

(b) Control impingement location case.

Figure 4: Average flow field obtained from Schlieren measurements.

In the Fig. 4 Schlieren visualization shows the global features of the uncontrolled and controlled interactions. The incident shock is generated by a 12 degree shock generator and the reflected shock is formed approxi-

mately $7\delta_{99}$ upstream of the impinging location of the incident shock on the wall for the uncontrolled interaction. Downstream of the interaction, it can be seen that the boundary layer is growing in thickness. The different shock impingement locations, as described in Section 2.2 were realised by translation of the shock generator along the longitudinal direction.

An inviscid flow analysis for the shock reflection at a freestream Mach number of 2 and an incident shock formed by a 12 degree shock generator, predicts a weak shock solution with pressure rise across the incident shock P_i/P_0 as 1.88, and the pressure rise over the entire interaction to be $P_f/P_0 = 2.7$.

Figure 5: Average flow field for without SCB and zero-impingement cases.

In Fig. 5 the streamwise velocity component for the uncontrolled case and the control impingement location case are compared, respectively. For this case, the measurement plane coincides with the symmetry plane of the flow field. The region of the immediate vicinity of the bump surface (0.1δ) is blanked out as the reflections did not allow to have a proper measurement. For the same reason, the region following the trailing edge of the bump is also blanked out.

In the uncontrolled case, the familiar mean features of the shock wave boundary layer interaction are observed. The incident shock wave impinges on the boundary layer up to the point where it reaches the sonic line. In the Fig.5, reversed flow is observed in the mean flow field of the uncontrolled case. In contrast, no separation bubble is observed in the case with the SCB, when the average flow properties are taken into the consideration.

Fig. 6 shows the difference in flow topology between cases without bump and bump with different shock impingement location, as visualized by the vertical velocity component normalized with the freestream velocity. The first thing that stands out when the bump is introduced, is the formation of the weak shock originating from the leading edge of the bump. At the location where leading edge shock meets the incident shock an additional shock-

Figure 6: Average wall normal component of velocity for (a) without SCB, (b) downstream impingement, (c) control impingement, and (d) upstream impingement cases.

Figure 7: Average streamwise velocity component and velocity profiles for (a) downstream impingement (b) control impingement, and (c) upstream impingement cases.

shock interaction occurs in the flow. The ramp face of the bump deflects the upstream supersonic flow, hence it is expected to see shock wave formation originating from the leading edge of the bump. The weak leading edge shock formation can be clearly seen in the cases where the impinging shock-reflected shock foot interaction effect is minor (See 6-b and 6-c). After evaluating the shock polars for the uncontrolled and controlled cases for the interactions with different impingement locations, the calculated overall pressure rise was found to be very similar

and approximately equal to $P_1/P_0=2.7$.

In Fig. 7 the velocity vectors are shown in combination with the U/U_∞ contour plot for the three different incident shock impingement location on the SCB. While for the control impingement and upstream impingement cases almost full recovery of the velocity profile is seen on the tail portion of the bump, the downstream impingement case demonstrates a steeper velocity profile. The first two cases reach a fuller boundary layer profile already on the tail portion of the bump. This can be explained by the fact that the interaction flow has been impacted less unfavourably, compared to the downstream-impingement case.

To establish the three-dimensionality and symmetry in the flow, the PIV measurements were repeated for all shock impingement locations at an off-center plane (See Sec. 2.2). The impact of the shock impingement location, as well as the three-dimensionality, were then evaluated in terms of the interaction length. For this purpose, the interaction length was determined for all cases and in both measurement planes. As first step two different window that includes the incident and separation shock respectively, are selected for each case. Knowing both streamwise and normal component of velocity, the shock locations are determined by obtaining the maximum change in streamwise velocity and the direction of the flow. Imposing these two conditions, corresponding x-coordinates for each y-coordinate is found for the points fulfill these conditions. By applying a linear fit for all the points, both impinging and reflected shock are detected in the respective selected windows. By extrapolating the shock in the selection window towards the wall, the interaction length is determined. The mean interaction length is decreased by around 2.3% for the control impingement case, being around 6.7δ for the symmetry plane and 6.5δ for the parallel off-center plane. Meanwhile for the upstream impingement and downstream impingement cases, respec-

tively, 8.5% and 15.8% increase is observed in the plane which is 5.8δ distant from the symmetry plane. This indicates the highly three-dimensional flow structure caused by the interaction between the SCB and SWBLI.

Figure 8: Shock detection process description.

3.2 Effects of the SCB on the interaction dynamics

High speed Schlieren measurements are used to reveal the effect of the bump and the shock impingement location on the flow dynamics, in particular the reflected shock unsteadiness.

The first step in the analysis of the shock position dynamics is to determine the shock location in each subsequent image. An appropriate interrogation window for the shock detection is selected for each configuration. Due to the knife-edge orientation it is expected that shocks appear darker in the picture. Therefore, first the elements that correspond to minimum intensity pixels in each row in the selected window are identified. Schlieren measurements integrate the density gradients over the full span of the test section and some three-dimensional effects, such as side-wall effects, influence the final image. This results in that the minimum intensity pixels cover an interval, corresponding to the appearance of a thick dark line in a Schlieren image. Therefore, a selection process is applied for detecting the shock for each row in the selected window and it is showed in Eq.1. In the equation P represents the intensity of each pixel and X is the location of the referred pixel. The detected shock location in each row is represented with X_{shock} .

$$X_{shock} = \frac{X_1(1/P_1) + \dots + X_n(1/P_n)}{1/P_1 + \dots + 1/P_n} \quad (1)$$

By applying a linear fit to all the points of the shock in the selected window, the reflected shock is detected. However, to avoid the contamination by noise in the detection process, a threshold is applied for the minimum intensity pixel search and only the largest intensity interval is taken into account for the detection of the shock

wave. Once shocks are determined in each image, to assess the effectiveness of SCB on reducing the unsteadiness of separation shock, the shock movements are analyzed in terms of both streamwise displacement and change in the shock angle. The results are shown in the Table 2. While the incident shock can be considered as steady, the separation shock exhibits higher oscillatory movements in both streamwise and rotational direction for the uncontrolled case.

In Fig. 9 the overall oscillations in the interaction region for each case is represented by means of the standard deviation of the Schlieren image gray-scale levels. It can be seen that the separation shock oscillations is considerably higher regarding to the cases with the bump installed in the flow. When the inviscid shock impingement location is set as the control point on the bump, the separation shock unsteadiness is reduced significantly particularly on rotational direction. The oscillatory movement of the originating point of the separation shock gives the combined information of the shock movements in both streamwise and rotational direction. While the uncontrolled case exhibits the highest separation shock unsteadiness, in cases with the bump the oscillatory movements of the separation shock is reduced (See Table 2).

The interaction length, defined as the distance between the inviscid impingement location of incident shock wave on the wall and the extrapolated origin of the separation shock wave, can be used to characterize the size of the separation bubble. As evident from Fig. 9, there is no appreciable unsteadiness of the incident shock wave observed. This implies that any change in the interaction length is directly proportional to the motion of the separation shock wave. However, the mean interaction length obtained from Schlieren measurements does not confirm this (See Table 3). This can be explained by the fact that Schlieren measurements integrate the density gradients over the full span of the test section. Therefore, a further investigation must be conducted to arrive to a conclusion on the point. Nevertheless, PIV measurements show decrease in the interaction length for cases with the bump compared to the uncontrolled case. The downstream-impingement case has smaller mean interaction length in both measurements. This might be explained by the fact that formation of the leading edge shock upstream of the separation shock weakens the strength of the latter.

Instantaneous flow fields of the cases uncontrolled and with the bump demonstrate the unstable nature of the separation bubble. In Ref. [9] Giepmans et al. explained the subtle distinction between the reversed flow and the separation bubble with the fact that while obtaining the zero-velocity iso-line is sufficient to determine the occurrence of flow reversal, the dividing streamline needs to be identified for defining the separation bubble. This makes the concept of the statistical occurrence of local flow reversal (or "separation probability") is a much less sensitive and

Cases	Separation Shock				Incident Shock		
	Mean	$std_{rotational}$	$std_{streamwise}$	$std_{originatingpoint}$	Mean	$std_{rotational}$	$std_{streamwise}$
No bump	40.7°	0.60°	0.21 δ	0.27 δ	-41.0°	0.23°	0.04 δ
Upstream impingement	41.1°	0.45°	0.16 δ	0.19 δ	-40.8°	0.23°	0.04 δ
Control impingement	41.1°	0.40°	0.18 δ	0.18 δ	-40.7°	0.23°	0.03 δ
Downstream impingement	41.4°	0.47°	0.20 δ	0.20 δ	-40.9°	0.21°	0.03 δ

Table 2: Mean shock angles and standard deviation in streamwise displacement and angular displacement

Cases	Schlieren		PIV
	$L_{interaction}$	$std_{L_{int}}$	$L_{interaction}$
No bump	7.8 δ	0.23 δ	7.7 δ
Upstream impingement	8.6 δ	0.19 δ	6.8 δ
Control impingement	8.5 δ	0.20 δ	6.7 δ
Downstream impingement	7.6 δ	0.19 δ	5.7 δ

Table 3: Interaction length found in the Schlieren and PIV measurements (symmetry plane).

Figure 9: Standard deviation of the flow field for all cases where the color scale increases from blue to red.

more practical approach for characterising the separation severity of the flow and also more suitable for comparing the different cases.

In this study, 300 instantaneous images are obtained for each case. From these images the local separation probability is calculated for each point on the selected window on each image. As explained previously, the separation criteria is connected to the occurrence of reversed flow. Fig.10 compares the spatial distribution of the sep-

aration probability, P_{sep} , for the bump with different impingement locations as well as for the interaction without bump. The percentages represents time fraction that reversed flow is encountered on that certain location.

Without any control method applied, 65% of the time flow is reversed in the region adjacent to the wall. Besides this, around 10% of the time reversed flow is observed at the height of approximately 1.5δ . This maximum height at which reversed flow is encountered in

the flow is reduced for all the cases with the bump even though the bump is also contributing to this with its own height. Moreover, all the cases with a bump exhibit a decrease in the peak value of the P_{sep} . For the downstream and upstream impingement cases with the SCB, the maximum P_{sep} value is reduced approximately to 40%. However, it is evident from Fig. 10, that the upstream impingement case exhibits a larger overall area of separation. As is shown in Fig. 6, while in the upstream impingement case the separation shock coincides with the leading edge shock, in the downstream impingement case leading edge shock decreases the strength of the separation shock. This would lead to a smaller area of separation which is more concentrated in the interaction region. The most remarkable change in the peak value of P_{sep} is observed for the zero-impingement case with the SCB. Only 20% of the time reversed flow is encountered in the vicinity of the shock impingement location on the bump surface.

Figure 10: Separation probability, P_{sep} , for all cases.

An average "separated area", A_{sep} , is calculated by spatially integrating the obtained separation probability, P_{sep} , over the flow domain [9]. This approach results in a more realistic estimation for an average area of flow separation at any instant of time, instead of calculating the separated flow area for the time-averaged flow field. A_{sep} is found approximately 86 mm^2 for the uncontrolled flow, while it is reduced to approximately 9 mm^2 for the control impingement case.

4. CONCLUSIONS

An experimental investigation was performed to improve the understanding of the effect of the interaction between SCB and SWBLI on the flow. The freestream flow conditions correspond to a Mach number of 2, a unit Reynolds number Re of 42×10^6 , and a momentum thickness Reynolds number Re_θ of 21.8×10^3 , while the shock generator's flow deflection angle is set to 12° .

High-speed Schlieren measurements are used to inves-

tigate the effect of the interaction of SCB and SWBLI on the flow dynamics, in particular the reflected shock unsteadiness. Measurements are performed for three different incident shock impingement locations on the bump surface and for the uncontrolled case. It was found that introducing the bump in the region of the shock wave boundary layer interaction improved the unsteady behaviour of the reflected shock. The control impingement location case showed 33% improvement in the reflected shock unsteadiness in the rotational direction compared to the uncontrolled interaction. On the other hand, the highest improvement in the unsteadiness in streamwise direction is observed for the upstream impingement case with approximately 24% decrease compared to the uncontrolled case.

Stereo-PIV measurements were performed to visualize the 3D flow organization in an uncontrolled oblique shock turbulent boundary layer interaction and the case of this interaction controlled by SCB. The investigation was carried out for all three different incident shock impingement locations on the bump surface and revealed that the control impingement and upstream impingement cases demonstrate a fuller boundary layer profile downstream of the interaction, which can be interpreted as that the interaction flow has been impacted less unfavourably compared to the downstream impingement case.

The probability of separation, P_{sep} , was determined for all cases, including the uncontrolled case. The minimum separation probability occurs for the control impingement location case with the bump with 20% P_{sep} . This indicates approximately 70% improvement compared to the uncontrolled case where the maximum value of P_{sep} is found 65%.

To improve the performance of the SCB in reducing the separation of the flow a further design modification on the bump geometry, in which the bump better "fills" the separation bubble, is proposed. In addition to this, it would be important to characterize the effect of installing a SCB in the interaction region on the overall drag to have the better assessment of the efficiency of the SCB as a control device.

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